

April 30, 2019

Impact of NPS fertilizer on the yield and yield components of Common Bean varieties in rainfed conditions of Pakistan

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Abstract

Low soil fertility is the major production constraints for common bean. A field experiment was conducted at National Agricultural Research Council (NARC), Islamabad, Pakistan during 2016- 2017 to study the impact of blended NPS levels on the yield and yield traits of common bean cultivars. The factors studied were six rates of blended NPS (0, 50, 100, 150, 200 and 250 kg ha⁻¹) that contain 19% N, 38% P₂O₅ and 7% S and three common bean varieties (Long Red Bean, Nasir, and Local Kashmir). The experiment was laid out in RCB design with split plot arrangements replicated thrice. Results showed that greatest branches and pods plant⁻¹ were recorded with 250 kg NPS ha⁻¹. Sub effect revealed that Long Red Bean gave the highest branches and pods plant⁻¹. Interactions revealed that Long Red Bean exhibited highest No. of days to flowering and physiological maturity with 200 - 250 kg NPS ha⁻¹. Long Red Bean gave maximum biomass and grain yield with 250 kg NPS ha⁻¹. It is concluded that Long Red Bean had high yield potential and best suited to agro-climatic conditions of NARC, Pakistan.

Keywords: *Phaseolus vulgaris* L, blended fertilizer, varieties, yield components, yield

Introduction

Common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) originated in Latin America and domesticated in Mexico more than 6000 years ago. It spread from Latin America to Europe, Africa and other parts of the world. In Pakistan, common bean is cultivated in barani and irrigated areas as well as tropics to the temperate regions (Alghamdi, 2007). Common bean is a warm season food legume crop and cannot grow well under a temperature below than 20°C. The optimum mean temperature for the common bean is 20 to 25°C. High temperatures interfere with seed setting while low temperature adversely affects its growth (Alghamdi & Ali, 2004). Common bean is a warm season food legume crop and cannot grow well under a temperature below than 20°C. The optimum mean temperature for the common bean is 20 to 25°C. High temperatures interfere with seed setting while low temperature adversely affects its growth (Alghamdi & Ali, 2004). Beans are well suited to small-scale production because they are relatively easy to manage (Amanullah & Muhammad, 2011). Production of common bean in Pakistan is insufficient to meet the domestic requirements; therefore the large amount is spent on its import every year. High yielding cultivars made self sufficient and enhanced the living standard of our farmers (Amanullah et al., 2006). Common bean yield depends on seed related factors like genetic makeup and quality along with agronomic factors such as sowing method, pesticide treatment (Chaudhry et al., 2006), crop rotations, tillage, cropping system, weed control, irrigation and fertilizer application (Kumar et al., 2009). Very few cultivars of the common bean are available in Pakistan. So the introduction of new highly productive germplasm is much needed which must be highly adaptable as well (Miles et al., 2007). Present work aimed to evaluate common bean germplasm locally in order to generate additional information for common bean utilization and adaptation. Different agroecological factor, soil conditions, and macro and micro nutrients are important features for bean production (Abebe, 2009). Yada (2011) investigated lower common bean yield due to less amount of N and P in the soils. Generally, increased grain yield was observed with 50 kg N ha⁻¹ and 60

April 30, 2019

kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ (Abebe, 2009). Among the nutrients, N limiting factor for plant growth and development (Veeresh, 2009). Deficiency in N caused decreased growth, branching, leaf yellowing and trifoliolate leaves in beans (CIAT, 1986). Research indicated that more than sixty percent of bean production was affected by NPS (Starling et al., 1998). Consequently, common bean is being generally considered as more responsive than other legumes to N fertilization (Gupta, 2000; Davis et al., 2009). However, nitrogenous activity declines with applied nitrogen, decreasing the sink strength, and hence, reduce the quantity of photo-assimilate partitioned to nodules and grain. The early application may also result in excessive vegetative growth leading to delayed flowering, reduced pod set, lower seed yield and a greater risk of disease infestation (Davis *et al.* 2009). Inorganic P had a positive effect on the yield and yield components of common bean. Redden and Herridge (2009) said that grain weight plant⁻¹ exhibited a marked response to P. Davis et al. (2009) observed a significant increase in grain weight per plant (8.65 g) due to increased P application up to 75 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹. Sulfur (S) is a very necessary nutrient for growth. It accumulated 0.2 to 0.5% in plant tissue on a dry matter basis (Ali and Khattak, 2008). Sulphur nutrition application not only increased growth rate but also improved the quality of the seed. (Gebeyehu and Daddy, 2003). This emphasizes the importance of developing an alternative means to meet the demand for nutrient in plants by using blending NPS. Though, no research was conducted common bean varieties to NPS fertilizer in NARC, Islamabad. Therefore, research was designed with the objective of NPS on the yield and yield components of common bean varieties in a rainfed environment of Islamabad, Pakistan.

Materials and methods

The experiment was conducted in 2016-17 at NARC, Islamabad, Pakistan (33° 42' N, 73° 10 E) in RCBD with the split-plot having three replications. Six blended NPS fertilizer rates, i.e., 0, 50, 100, 150, 200 and 250 kg ha⁻¹ (Table 1) were kept in main and three varieties (Long Red Bean, Local Kashmir, and Nasir) in sub-plots. Each experimental unit consists of 4 rows measuring 4 meters in length. Row to row distance was kept at 50 cm and plant to plant distance at 10 cm, respectively. Data were recorded on days maturity (DM), Days to flowering (DF), plant height (PH), number of branches plant⁻¹ (NB), number of pod plant⁻¹ (NP), number of seeds pod⁻¹ (NOS), 100 seed weight, Grain yield (GY) and above-ground dry biomass yield (BY), according to the descriptor of common bean (IBPGR, 1982).

Statistical Data Analysis

Data were analyzed by Statistix 10. Least significant difference tests were applied where data were found statistically significant according to MSTATC software.

Results and discussion

Days to flowering

ANOVA showed that days to reach 50% flowering had a significant response to blended NPS, varieties and their interactions (Table 3). Results revealed that Long Red Bean gave a maximum number of days to flowering with 250 kg NPS ha⁻¹ but earliest days to flowering was recorded in Local Kashmir (Table 4). Local Kashmir was found to be early maturing as compared to the other varieties across all NPS rates. This result was in line with the findings of Dargie, (2015) who reported that increasing N rate significantly prolonged the days to 50% flowering. This might be due to the fact that excessive supply of N promotes luxuriant and succulent vegetative growth, dominating the reproductive phase. This result is corroborated by that of Tewari and Singh (2000) who investigated that common bean with 150 kg N ha⁻¹ needed more number of days to 50% flowering as compared to 40 and 80 kg N ha⁻¹. This result is also in contrast to the finding of Tedesse, (2012) who reported non-significant interaction effects of nitrogen and sulphur on days to flowering of common bean.

Physiological maturity

A number of days to physiological maturity was significantly affected by blended NPS and interaction, but varieties were not significant (Table 3). Increase in blended NPS from 0 to 250 kg ha⁻¹ had a significant increase in the number of days required to reach physiological maturity. A higher number of days required to reach physiological maturity was recorded with 250 kg NPS ha⁻¹ for Long Red Bean while the shortest was recorded in control for variety Local Kashmir (Table 5). The results indicated that days to maturity in most cases were prolonged in increased NPS rates that promoted vegetative growth. This is in line with the results of Gupta and Sharma, (2000) who reported that nitrogen promoted vegetative and lush growth thereby delaying plant maturity of onion. This indicated that the nutrients taken up by plant roots from the soil were used for increased cell division and synthesis of carbohydrate (Mehlich, 1984). Tedesse, (2012) reported a significant effect on days to maturity on common bean.

Plant height

Plant height was significantly effected by NPS rates, varieties and their interaction (Table 3). Nasir had higher plant height with 150 kg NPS ha⁻¹ among the other combinations (Table 6). Enhanced plant height might be due to the maximum vegetative growth under higher NPS. Our results are line with the findings of Moniruzzaman, *et al.* (2008) who investigated that plant height increased with the highest phosphorus level (120 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹). Highest plant height might also be ascribed of better root formation due to sulphur, which in turn activated higher absorption of N, P, K and sulphur from soil and improved metabolic activity inside the plant (Jawahar *et al.*, 2017). Similar results were reported by Jawahar *et al.*, (2017) who reported that sulphur @ 30 kg ha⁻¹ gave maximum plant height, LAI, chlorophyll content and number of branches per plant. Similarly, Turuko and Mohammed, (2014) and Negash and Rezene, (2015) also reported that P rate at 0 -40 kg ha⁻¹ had a significant effect on plant height in common bean.

Branches per plant⁻¹

The analysis of variance confirmed significant response to main and sub effects on a number of primary branches, but the interactions were non significant (Table 3). Results revealed that Long Red Bean produced the highest primary branches plant⁻¹ (2.55) while the lowest was recorded in a variety of Local Kashmir (Table 7). This was due to the genetic makeup of the varieties. The result is line with the findings of Asrat, (2013) who investigated that maximum branches per plant could be obtained with the highest rate of NPS. Mean for revealed that NPS at the rate of 250 kg ha⁻¹ gave maximum primary branches. Shubhashree, (2007) suggested a number of branches with 70 kg NPS ha⁻¹ over control.

No. of pods/plant

ANOVA shows that pods were significantly influenced by NPS and varieties (Table 3). NPS @ 250 kg ha⁻¹ gave the highest No. of pods per plant (Table 7). Highest pods/plant with a higher value of NPS ascribed of more number of primary branches and plant height contributed to a higher number of pods. Moniruzzaman *et al.* (2008) reported a significant increase in pods with NPS. Deshbhratar *et al.*, (2010) and Tesfaye and Balcha (2015) investigated that phosphorus application at 75 kg ha⁻¹ significantly increased the number of pods per plant. Researchers observed that phosphorus promoted the formation of nodes and pods in legumes (Buttery, 1969). Means for varieties revealed that Long Red Bean had higher pods plant⁻¹. The variation was due to genetic make up of the varieties for producing pods (Fageria *et al.*, 2010).

Hundred seed weight (g)

April 30, 2019

The analysis of variance revealed that 100-seed was significantly affected by NPS, varieties and NPS \times V interaction (Table 3). Interaction revealed that Long Red Bean with 200 kg NPS ha⁻¹ had heaviest seed weight among the other treatments (Table 8). It was probably due to fertilizer -use-efficiency of the N, P, and S by common bean crop. Our results are line with the finding of Shamim and Naimat (1987) who observed that P content in the seeds, as well as the formation of fat and albumin, had a positive impact on 100-seed weight. The nutrient plays in regenerative growth of the crop (Zafar et al., 2013), leading to increased seed size, which has improved 100- seed weight. Girma et al. (2014) and Zafar et al. (2013) found a significant influence of P on thousand seed weight of bean varieties.

Above-ground dry biomass yield

Bio-mass had a significant response to NPS and interaction (Table 3). Data showed that Long Red Bean with 250 kg NPS ha⁻¹ gave highest bio-mass among the other combinations (Table 9). Maximum bio-mass could be due to yield components such as pods/plant and seed weight. Singh and Singh (2000) and Veeresh, (2003) suggested that enhanced bio-mass was due to the maximum level of NPS. This result was in line with that of Agegrew and Fessehaie (2006) and Tedesse, (2012) they reported a linear response of bio-mass to P and sulphur.

Grain yield

Grain yield had a significant response to NPS, variety, and interaction (Table 3). Long Red Bean with 250 kg NPS produced the highest grain yield (Table 10). Highest yield might be due to better availability of P from the soil solution and translocated to crop for grain formation (Mourice and Tryphone, 2012; Mulugeta, 2011) . Negash and Rezene (2015) reported improved grain yield with a higher level of NPS.

Conclusion

Thus, it can be concluded that Long Red Bean with NPS at 200 kg ha⁻¹ was better and can be used for common bean production in rainfed conditions of Pakistan

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April 30, 2019

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April 30, 2019

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April 30, 2019

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April 30, 2019

Table 1. Physico-chemical properties of the experimental soil

Characteristics	Values
Sand	151 g kg ⁻¹
Silt	450 g kg ⁻¹
Clay	400 g kg ⁻¹
Electrical conductivity (EC)	2.66 dSm ⁻¹
Soil pH (1:1)	7.80
Organic Matter	0.89 %
NO ₃ -N	5.52 mg kg ⁻¹
Available K (mg kg ⁻¹)	180 mg kg ⁻¹ soil
AB-DTPA extractable P	7.8 mg kg ⁻¹ soil
Total N	0.99 g kg ⁻¹ soil

Table 1. Rate of fertilizer and their nutrient content (kg ha⁻¹) treatments for the experiment

No	Blended NPS Fertilizer rate (kg ha ⁻¹)	N	P ₂ O ₅	S
1	0 kg NPS	0	0	0
2	50 kg NPS	9.5	19	3.5
3	100 kg NPS	19	38	7
4	150 kg NPS	28.5	57	10.5
5	200 kg NPS	38	76	14
6	250 kg NPS	47.5	95	17.5

Table 3. Analysis of variance (mean squares) of days to flowering (DF), days maturity (DM), plant height (PH), number of branches plant- 1 (NB), number of pod plant-1 (NP), 100-seed weight (HSW), above-ground dry biomass yield (BY) and Grain yield (GY) during 2016-2017 growing season.

Source	d.f	DF	DM	PH	NB	NP	HSW	BY (kg ha ⁻¹)	GY (kg ha ⁻¹)
Replication	2	1.69	19.24	11.51	0.78	3.41	24.02	5250116	240627
NPS rate	5	153.57**	8.07ns	9134.41**	1.14*	115.13**	1743.46**	3038612 ^{ns}	351493*
Variety (V)	2	2.20*	19.74**	211.29*	0.2 ^{ns}	11.76 ^{ns}	1181.52**	4756008*	305109*
NPS × V	10	5.32**	9.23ns	1023.8**	1.75**	56.55**	257.75**	21617511**	1097684**
Error	34	0.9	4.4	68.1	0.16	10.64	11.29	2129268	89844

*, **, Significant at 5% and 1% level of probability, respectively. ns, No-significant difference at 5%.

Table 2. Mean a number of days to the flower of the common bean as affected by the interaction of variety and blended NPS fertilizer rates during the 2016-2017 growing season.

Variety	NPS rate (kg ha ⁻¹)						Mean
	0	50	100	150	200	250	
Long Red Bean	45.33 ^{abc}	45.33 ^{abc}	45.33 ^{abc}	45.33 ^{abc}	46.33 ^{ab}	46.67 ^a	45.72
Nasir	45.67 ^{abc}	45.00 ^{bc}	45.33 ^{abc}	45.67 ^{abc}	46.67 ^a	44.67 ^c	40.50
Local Kashmir	41.67 ^d	38.33 ^e	39.67 ^e	39.67 ^e	42.00 ^d	42.00 ^d	45.50
Mean	44.22	42.89	43.44	43.56	45.00	44.33	
LSD (0.05)							1.58
A CV (%)							2.20

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different as judged by LSD test at 5%, CV= coefficient of variation

Table 3. Mean a number of days to physiological maturity of the common bean as affected by the interaction of variety and blended NPS fertilizer rates during the 2016-2017 growing season.

Variety	NPS rate (kg ha ⁻¹)						Mean
	0	50	100	150	200	250	
Long Red Bean	96.00 ^{a-d}	93.33 ^{de}	98.00 ^{abc}	98.67 ^{ab}	94.00 ^{cde}	99.33 ^a	96.56
Nasir	96.33 ^{a-d}	95.67 ^{a-d}	94.00 ^{cde}	95.33 ^{a-d}	98.00 ^{abc}	93.33 ^{de}	95.44
Local Kashmir	91.33 ^e	95.67 ^{a-d}	95.00 ^{b-e}	97.33 ^{a-d}	98.67 ^{ab}	98.00 ^{abc}	96.00
Mean	94.56	94.89	95.67	97.11	96.89	96.89	
LSD (0.05)							3.48
A CV (%)							2.2

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different as judged by LSD test at 5%, CV= coefficient of variation

April 30, 2019

Table 4. Means of plant height (cm) of the common bean as affected by the interaction of variety and blended NPS fertilizer rates during the 2016-2017 growing season.

Variety	NPS rate (kg ha ⁻¹)						Mean
	0	50	100	150	200	250	
Long Red Bean	56.30 ^{cd}	83.44 ^{bc}	75.12 ^{cd}	85.58 ^{abc}	89.71 ^{abc}	91.97 ^{ab}	80.35
Nasir	63.13 ^{de}	57.17 ^{efg}	88.94 ^{abc}	99.72 ^a	90.69 ^{abc}	90.52 ^{abc}	81.69
Local Kashmir	31.08 ⁱ	38.57 ^{hi}	43.33 ^{ghi}	45.6 ^{gh}	48.96 ^{fgh}	48.55 ^{fgh}	42.83
Mean	50.17	59.73	69.13	77.27	76.45	77.01	
LSD (0.05)	13.69						
A CV (%)	12.00						

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different as judged by LSD test at 5%, CV= coefficient of variation

Table 7. Mean a number of pods per plant and seeds per pod of the common bean as influenced by varieties and blended NPS fertilizer rates during the 2016-2017 growing season.

Treatments	Number of primary branches per plant	Number of pods per plant
Variety		
Long Red Bean	2.55 ^a	15.30 ^a
Nasir	2.28 ^{ab}	12.63 ^{ab}
Local Kashmir	2.05 ^b	10.24 ^c
LSD (0.05)	0.28	2.21
NPS rate (kg ha ⁻¹)		
0	1.56 ^d	8.70 ^c
50	2.05 ^c	11.82 ^{bc}
100	2.25 ^{ab}	12.6 ^{ab}
150	2.55 ^a	12.51 ^{ab}
200	2.58 ^a	14.91 ^{ab}
250	2.77 ^a	18.52 ^a
LSD (0.05)	0.38	3.14
CV (%)	17.7	25.1

Means in columns and rows followed by the same letter are not significantly different judged by LSD test at 5% level of significance; ns = non significant, CV= coefficient of variation

Table 8. Means of hundred seed weight (g) of the common bean as influenced by the interaction of variety and blended NPS fertilizer rates during the 2016-2017 growing season.

Variety	NPS rate (kg ha ⁻¹)						Mean
	0	50	100	150	200	250	
Long Red Bean	38.33 ^c	40.00 ^c	38.33 ^c	38.33 ^c	54.33 ^a	46.67 ^b	42.67
Local Kashmir	23.33 ^e	23.33 ^e	38.33 ^c	20.00 ^e	21.67 ^e	42.33 ^{bc}	28.17
Nasir	21.67 ^e	20.00 ^e	20.00 ^e	20.00 ^e	31.67 ^d	30.00 ^d	23.89
Mean	27.78	27.78	32.22	26.11	35.89	39.67	
LSD (0.05)	5.58						
A CV (%)	10.6						

Means in columns and rows followed by the same letters are not significantly different as judged by LSD test at 5% level of significance — Cv=Coefficient of variation.

Table 9. Means of above-ground dry biomass yield (kg ha⁻¹) of the common bean as influenced by the interaction of variety and blended NPS fertilizer rates during the 2016-2017 growing season.

Variety	NPS rate (kg ha ⁻¹)						Mean
	0	50	100	150	200	250	
Long Red Bean	5794 ^{def}	5178 ^e	9135 ^{ab}	5798 ^{def}	6191 ^{c-f}	10278 ^a	7062.33
Local Kashmir	4129 ^f	4936 ^f	5724 ^{def}	6527 ^{b-f}	8802 ^{abc}	7329 ^{b-e}	6241.17
Nasir	4045 ^f	6443 ^{b-f}	6640 ^{b-f}	5782 ^{def}	8073 ^{a-d}	9073 ^{ab}	6676
Mean	4656	5519	7166.33	6035.67	7688.67	8893.33	
LSD (0.05)	2421.3						
A CV (%)	21.9						

Means in columns and rows followed by the same letters are not significantly different as judged by LSD test at 5% level of significance. CV= coefficient of variation

April 30, 2019

Table 10. Means of grain yield (kg ha^{-1}) of the common bean as influenced by the interaction of variety and blended NPS fertilizer rates during the 2016-2017 growing season.

Variety	NPS rate (kg ha^{-1})						Mean
	0	50	100	150	200	250	
Long Red Bean	2485 ^{cde}	2360 ^e	2582 ^{b-e}	3044 ^{abc}	2558 ^{b-e}	3260 ^a	2715
Local Kashmir	1700 ^g	2249 ^{ef}	2389 ^{de}	2521 ^{b-e}	3053 ^{abc}	3079 ^{ab}	2499
Nasir	1763 ^{fg}	2500 ^{b-e}	2747 ^{a-e}	2250 ^{ef}	2956 ^{a-d}	2505 ^{b-e}	2453
Mean	1983	2370	2573	2605	2856	2948	
LSD (0.05)							497.4
A CV (%)							11.7

Means within columns and rows followed by the same letter are not significantly different as judged by LSD test at 5% level of significance. CV= Coefficient of Variation.